

MathMovesU Event

Credit: NOIRLab/NSF/AURA/R. Sparks

Robert T. Sparks

NSF's NOIRLab partnered with Raytheon and the University of Arizona Office of Early Academic Outreach for MathMovesU day on 10 February 2020. Over 200 middle school students from schools around Tucson built their own Galileoscope and learned about careers in STEM fields.

Since the partnership began in 2010, NOAO (and now NOIRLab) has partnered with Raytheon to build Galileoscopes every year (except 2019 when Galileoscopes were temporarily unavailable and MathMovesU built Snap Circuits® as a temporary replacement). Over 3,200 students have built Galileoscopes over the course of this partnership. Raytheon recently hired its first engineer who built a Galileoscope at a previous MathMovesU event.

The Galileoscope was created for the International Year of Astronomy in 2009 to commemorate 400 years since Galileo embarked on his historic observations. Over

250,000 Galileoscopes have been distributed worldwide. It is a small, low-cost telescope designed to have a similar size and magnification to telescopes used by Galileo but with a modern optical design. The telescope was designed by a team of engineers, astronomers, and educators, with NOAO staff playing a key role in the design and in the production of educational materials to accompany the Galileoscope. The Galileoscope kit comes with two eyepieces: a modern Plössl eyepiece (yielding a magnification of 25x) and a Galilean-style eyepiece. The eyepieces can be combined to create a Barlow lens doubling the magnification of the telescope to 50x.

At MathMovesU day, NOIRLab staff led the Galileoscope build while members of Raytheon's Leadership Development program (called LDPs) assisted students with building telescopes and talked with them about careers in STEM fields. The LDPs are early-career engineers at

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Raytheon learning the skills needed to succeed in their careers. The LDPs learn how to build Galileoscopes at a workshop conducted by NOIRLab staff before the MathMovesU event.

During the build, students learn about the Six Sigma process for quality control. This process is used by companies worldwide to detect and remove defects before the final product. Students have several checkpoints where they must inspect the Galileoscope before continuing the build. Students must sign off that they did the procedure correctly, and the LDP must also perform an inspection and verify that the student's work is correct.

The Galileoscope can be used to recreate Galileo's observations of the Moon, Venus, Jupiter, Saturn, and many other objects in the night sky. Each student takes home their Galileoscope and a tripod to continue their exploration of the night sky.